

ON THE ROLE OF LENGTHSCALE IN THE PREDICTION OF FAILURE OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES: ASSESSMENT AND NEEDS

S. Mark Spearing, Paul A. Lagace and Hugh L. N. McManus
TECHNOLOGY LABORATORY FOR ADVANCED COMPOSITES
Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics
Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Cambridge, Massachusetts 02139, USA

ABSTRACT

The role of modeling in the design of structural composite components against failure is discussed. Composite materials fail due to damage processes operating at several lengthscales. The interactions between these processes offer the principal challenges to applying mechanism-based models at structural scales beyond the ply level. A methodology is proposed to increase the efficiency of the design process, analogous to the "building block" approach, which provides a framework for integrating mechanism-based models with the current experimentally-based design process. Available models are reviewed and their key elements identified. General concepts are illustrated via a discussion of the particular issues pertaining to notched components. Key steps needed to allow the evolution of the design process to the envisioned process are identified.

INTRODUCTION

Efficient, cost-effective design is vital to realizing the potential of composite materials for structural applications. However, the existing design methodology, particularly for design against failure, is poorly suited to the increasingly cost-conscious operating climate. Two of the keys to achieving such efficient and cost-effective designs are, firstly, to fully utilize the ability to tailor composite properties by choice of fiber, matrix, architecture, etc., and secondly, to be able to iterate on the design rapidly and accurately. The methodology, with regard to failure, is currently lacking in both these respects. As a consequence, the design process is slow, excessively conservative and often struggles to reach a satisfactory, let alone good, design. The underlying cause of these shortcomings is the empirical nature of the current design process for composite structures. In particular, there is a general lack of recognition as to the role of *lengthscale* in the failure process.

The current "building block" methodology [1], as illustrated in Fig. 1, consists of transferring experimentally determined "allowable stresses" (or other parameters) from one scale (e.g. test coupon, element, component and structure) to another to allow design to proceed at the next. This procedure involves many experiments and usually results in a safe design. However, it is generally a one-way process. If observations are made at a high level (i.e. structural or component) that indicate a change may be necessary at a lower level (i.e. the choice of fibers, matrix, or fiber architecture), there are two possible outcomes. If it is decided that the change would lead to a better (i.e. more efficient) design but that the current design is satisfactory (i.e. passes all requirements), then the cost of restarting the process at some lower level would likely rule out the change. In the second case, when the current design is not satisfactory, there is no alternative but to restart the process at the coupon level. In either case, the designer is denied the use of the previously obtained experimental data to streamline the process of iteration and excessive cost is incurred.

Figure 1. Flowchart for the "Building Block" approach for structural composite design/certification.

We believe it is necessary to re-examine the design process, and thus we propose a more efficient process, as shown in the flowchart of Fig. 2. This will be discussed in more detail in section 6, but there are two key points that need to be emphasized. Firstly, the structural design process should begin at the constituent level, with the choice of fiber, matrix and fiber architecture (including processing considerations), and secondly, that the progression from one level to the next should utilize mechanism-based models as well as experimental results.

Figure 2. Flowchart for the proposed desired design process.

Models, and modeling schemes, exist for taking micromechanical data and presenting the results in the form of criteria for failure that can be used in conjunction with numerical methods for structural design [2,3]. However, this modeling tends to adopt a form which is independent of lengthscale. A continuum mechanics approach has been well proved for metals and it is widely incorporated into numerical methods. Unfortunately, the assumption of scale-independence is contrary to the behavior of most composites, and even when models do introduce a lengthscale, it tends to take the form of an experimentally determined curve-fitting parameter which may not have physical significance. Examples of models of this type are the correlations for notched strength [4,5] which can provide good fits to experimental data, but provide little insight as to how the test results at the laminate and subelement levels relate to the design choices made at the lower levels of fiber and ply. There are models that describe the damage processes which affect failure. However, these mechanism-based models have been derived at the lower levels of lengthscale (fiber and ply) and have not been successfully applied to design at higher structural levels of lengthscale (laminate to structure).

In this paper, we will examine the damage mechanisms operating at distinct lengthscales that contribute to the failure of composite structures, particularly in the context of explicitly incorporating models for them in the design process as proposed in Fig. 2.

MECHANISM-BASED MODELING

The advantage of physical, mechanism-based models is that they provide a true predictive capability, as distinct from the interpolative function of empirical models. The pursuit of a pure mechanism-based model is a noble, yet pragmatically unrealistic and unobtainable, goal. Our understanding of the behavior of materials is always based, at some level, on experimental observations and general experience. Thus, just as for monolithic materials, it is likely that these models will include some empirical elements. However, they should retain sufficient physical basis that they form a solid framework upon which to superpose empirical descriptions. A key element of these models is, therefore, that they should incorporate the physical mechanisms controlling the failure process. As will become clear, several coupled damage mechanisms may operate. It is thus particularly important to assess the relative contribution of each.

In the context of this paper, we concern ourselves with models that satisfy the requirements of a physical basis, although we acknowledge that subsequent tuning and calibration with experimental data will probably be necessary to achieve the desired level of accuracy. The choices of the "starting" lengthscale and the other lengthscales of evaluation depend upon aspects of practicality and usefulness. In some sense, these choices represent the "levels of homogenization" at which it is useful to deal with the structure. In passing on the information and knowledge for each of these levels, characterizations of the previous levels are important. The behavior at different levels will require very different characterizations. The choice of these metrics is key since the chosen metric must have pertinence to the immediately higher and lower level and possibly to further levels. It is also preferable that these metrics, which serve as input parameters for the models, be directly measurable quantities. Ashby [6] has provided a good overview of this philosophy of modeling materials problems.

BASIC DAMAGE MECHANISMS

The processes that govern damage, its effects, and final failure in composites operate at several lengthscales. Since these are inherently fracture processes, the models must be formulated using the particular controlling lengthscale associated with them. In this section, we briefly examine the role of the lengthscales in determining the damage mechanisms prevalent in composites up to the laminate level.

Tensile Strength (fiber-controlled): The tensile strength of carbon, glass and ceramic fibers exhibit a dependence on the gauge length and fiber radius [7] that can be usefully described by weakest link statistics [8]. In order to predict the strength of a composite ply, the length-dependence of strength of individual fibers is modified by the elastic and shear transfer properties of the fiber, matrix and interface [9,10]. Such models allow a reasonably accurate prediction of the tensile strength of a unidirectional composite ply and they provide a clear, physical basis for some of the experimentally observed "size effects" in composite strength [11].

Tensile Strength (matrix-controlled): Physically-based models have been used, successfully, to predict matrix fracture [12,13] in unidirectional plies of brittle matrix composites. Again, the controlling lengthscale is the fiber radius, but modified according to the stress transfer properties of the interface and fracture properties of the matrix. As an example of the utility of the basic model [12], it gives insight as to why unidirectional ceramic matrix composites (CMC) experience this form of cracking whereas polymer matrix composites (PMC) generally do not. The key feature is that the effective lengthscale in PMC's is several orders of magnitude less than that for CMC's. The contributing parameters to this lengthscale are the fiber radius, volume fraction, matrix toughness, relative moduli, and interfacial shear stress. This leads to a PMC matrix cracking stress higher than that for fiber fracture, whereas in CMC's the reverse is true.

Off-Axis Ply Cracking: In laminated composites, the cracking of off-axis plies has been extensively modeled [14-17]. The work has clearly shown that the controlling lengthscale is the thickness of the plies, modified by the constitutive behavior of the material. It follows that thick plies crack at lower stress levels than thin plies.

Delamination: Delamination is a failure mode unique to laminated media. Delamination initiation depends on flaws on the scale of the ply thickness and the stresses acting at this scale. The stress-based model of Brewer and Lagace [18] and accompanying experimental results suggests a controlling lengthscale of this order. Delamination growth can be modeled by the energy considerations of fracture mechanics [19,20], with a controlling lengthscale that can lie somewhere between the ply thickness (for purely thermal loading) to the length of the delamination crack.

In the preceding paragraphs, the mechanism-based models which give predictions, with suitable accuracy, for the stresses required to induce each damage mechanism, have been highlighted. A key to this modeling approach is the recognition that specific lengthscales control each damage process, from the fiber radius through to the structural scale. Furthermore, the models that are based on fracture mechanics (bridged matrix cracks, off axis ply cracks and delamination growth) are readily extended to predict fatigue damage propagation, giving additional predictive capability from the same modeling framework [14]. However, adequate models do not currently exist to deal with the interactions between damage modes. This is a key element that is missing from the overall design process. For example, in addition to the loss of stiffness associated with off-axis ply cracking, the formation of such cracks can precipitate other failure modes such as delamination at the interface with neighboring plies [21,22] or fiber fracture at the edge of the off-axis ply crack within the neighboring plies [23]. This, in turn, influences the tensile strength [24]. It then becomes necessary to consider the lengthscales of the interactions as well as those of the damage modes in isolation.

In the context of the desired design process shown in Fig. 2, the next step is to apply such micromechanical models to predict failure at higher structural levels/lengthscales. As an illustration, we examine techniques for predicting the response of a notched tensile panel and the potential utilization of the micromechanics described here.

NOTCHED STRENGTH AT THE LAMINATE LEVEL

It is widely recognized that the tensile strength of notched composites is dependent on the lengthscale. Experimental studies [25] suggest that a straightforward application of linear elastic fracture mechanics may be appropriate in the case of very thick laminates, implying that the controlling lengthscale in these cases is the notch size. However, for most composite systems a single value of the fracture toughness does not represent the data well. Widely-used empirical models such as the Whitney-Nuismer [4] and Mar-Lin [5] correlations take different approaches but ultimately fulfill the same function of relating the strength to the notch size. Various workers have added extra parameters which improve the quality of the fit to the data, but without improving the physical basis [26].

None of these correlative approaches satisfies the intention of providing models that permit efficient progression and iteration in the design process. The parameters of notched strength correlations are only tenuously linked to the damage processes that underpin failure. This point is clearly illustrated by looking at the radiograph of a notched coupon, shown in Fig. 3, that has

been loaded in tension to a load level below ultimate failure. Damage in the form of splits, off-axis ply cracks, and delamination is visible. Fiber fractures (not visible in the radiograph) have also begun to accumulate. Experimental and analytical studies [27-31] have shown how such damage can redistribute the notch tip stresses and thereby play an important role in the failure process and final failure stress.

Figure 3. Radiograph of a center-notched $[90/\pm 45/0]_s$ laminate loaded in uniaxial tension to 90% of the static failure stress showing axial splitting, off-axis ply cracking and delamination around the notch tips.

As has already been discussed, the development of each damage mode is determined at a separate lengthscale. In addition, some of the damage modes interact - off-axis ply cracks locally fracture 0° fibers while splits together with neighboring delaminations reduce the notch tip stress concentration in the 0° ply. Even without these interactions, different lengthscales are pertinent: fiber fracture occurs at the fiber scale; off-axis ply cracking is governed by the ply thickness; and splitting, delamination, and the notch tip stress field are determined by the notch size and the ply thickness. Clearly, a model which connects the notched strength to the underlying damage processes must explicitly include the effect of each of these controlling lengthscales. Conversely, the correlative models for notched strength, which relate strength to a single lengthscale, the notch size or some averaging size, do not have a complete physical basis.

As yet, there has been little success directly accounting for the notched strength using mechanism-based models. Those models which do exist [30,31] have been derived for specific material systems with specific observed damage modes. Although these models provide useful insights as to the role of damage in determining notched strength, they have yet to be generalized to provide the wider modeling capability that we are advocating. An alternative approach, that has met with some success, is to use progressive damage models [e.g. 32] in which the elastic property changes are interpreted as a metric of the homogenized damage state. The main attraction of this approach is that it is readily implemented in finite element methods. However, in applying this concept, great care must be taken to ensure that the relevant lengthscales of the fracture processes are adequately represented.

THE STRUCTURAL LEVEL

There is more experience and success progressing from the subelement to the component and structural scales. For example, Lagace et al [33,34], have shown that a notched strength correlation [4,5], based on test data obtained on flat tensile coupons, can be utilized to predict the burst pressure of notched composite pressure vessels, so long as the failure processes remain the same. The procedure to do this follows well-established methods of structural analysis. In

particular, it is important to correctly use composite shell theory in order to extend the correlation from flat plates to curved, pressurized shells and thus take into account the particular structural effects introduced by the configuration. Recent theoretical work [35] has shown that in order to use the same approach to predict the failure pressure of relatively large radius, thin-walled pressure vessels such as aircraft fuselages, it is vital to include the effects of the geometric nonlinearity caused by pressure-induced bulging of the notch flanks. This additional consideration can be ascribed to the change in the ratio of the wall thickness to the tube radius, reflecting yet another lengthscale effect.

The important point is that it is currently possible to progress from the laminate/subelement level (a notched tensile coupon) to a structural component level (a small notched pressure vessel) and, in principle, to the structural level (an aircraft fuselage). The models available for correlating the notched strength are suitable for making this connection because they capture the effects of the relevant failure processes at the homogenized laminate level, so long as these processes and their relative importance do not change between the laminate (coupon) and structural level.

ASSESSMENT AND NEEDS

In the preceding sections, we have briefly summarized the models available that might allow progression and iteration within the design process, focusing particularly on those relevant to structures containing notches. Models do exist, at the scales below that of the laminate (coupon), that have some utility for predicting failure. However, they are not sufficient to make predictions, *a priori*, of the failure response at higher levels. In particular, relatively little attention has been devoted to modeling the interactions between damage modes. This is reflected in the models that are used at the coupon and subelement levels which have little grounding in the underlying mechanisms of failure. The models which are available at the subelement level, such as for notched coupons in our example, do permit design at higher levels. The critical disconnect in modeling capability occurs between ply level models and those at the laminate/subelement level.

In essence, the designer needs to be able to predict and iterate from all levels of the design process. In addition, it is becoming increasingly important that the design process start at a lower level: with the choices of fibers, matrix, interface and an associated appropriate processing technology. This capability is necessary to take advantage of the increasingly wide array of fiber and matrix materials, the improvements in processing technology (that, for example, permit automated tow and fiber placement), and the increasing premium placed on cost-efficient design. Our vision of this design process is illustrated in Fig. 2. In some respects, this diagram parallels that of the building block approach shown in Fig. 1. An important part of the process is still to perform experiments at each level. However, the approaches differ in two key respects. Firstly, the desired design process starts at a lower design level than the building block approach. Secondly, the two-way arrows, signifying prediction and iteration, reflect embedded mechanism-based models, rather than just experimental results as in the current process.

In order to achieve this desired design process, models are needed to permit scaling of failure predictions through the progression from the constituent level to the overall structural configuration. Existing models for the observed damage mechanisms should be used as a starting point. However, additional model development for the basic failure mechanisms and their interactions clearly needs to be undertaken. One challenge is, then, to extend and link existing models so that they can support experimental results. The other principal challenge is to embed enough of the physical basis of these models such that the ability to iterate through the initial stages of the design process is retained while not overcomplicating the models at the higher levels which currently provide a useful means of progressing towards a final design.

With reference to the example that we have pursued herein, that of designing structures which contain notches, notched strength correlations, such as the Mar-Lin correlation, permit a useful prediction from the subelement (laminate) to the structural level as long as the behavior stays within certain bounds. A logical way to progress might be to express the parameters of such correlations, if possible, as functions of the physical parameters that dictate failure. The micromechanical models described herein illustrate what some of these baseline parameters are. Even if the connection has to be made via experiments, it will at least ensure that an increased

physical basis has been obtained. In this sense, we are advocating an evolutionary rather than revolutionary change from the current process.

CLOSING REMARKS

Several concepts have been conveyed that are important in order to increase the efficiency of the design process with regard to failure of composite structures. Current design methodologies for failure critical items are often inefficient because they rely on purely empirical methods and thus do not permit iteration within the design cycle. In response to these shortcomings, we have proposed a desired design process. This differs from the widely used "building block approach" in that it includes mechanism-based models for the failure processes with the express realization that different damage modes operate at different lengthscales as do the interactions of such damage modes.

Specific needs have been identified to allow such a design process to evolve. Some of the models at the heart of the process currently exist and form a basis on which to build a better understanding and to extend these models. One of the principal challenges associated with this approach is the fact that damage mechanisms operate at several different lengthscales with interactions between these mechanisms also at different lengthscales. There is a general lack of models for such interaction between damage modes. Such mechanism-based models need to be reduced to a form that is consistent with existing higher-level models. This must be achieved while retaining the physical, lengthscale-dependent, basis of each of the models.

The development of the desired design methodology presented here must be an evolutionary process and will thus have both short- and long-term benefits. In the short term current mechanistic models can be used to bound problems, identify critical material properties, and map likely failure modes. This will allow improved test programs which concentrate on critical properties, failure modes, and key lengthscales. Since the models must be based on experimentally-observed phenomena, experimental results will help to improve these models and there will thus be a synergistic effect. In the longer term, improved modeling will allow designers to begin the design process with the choice, or even design, of constituent materials and interfaces and then proceed with the prediction of the performance and failure at the various lengthscales (i.e. ply, laminate, structural component, full scale structure). Existing design methodology at the higher structural lengthscales will thus be supported and justified by fundamental understanding at lower lengthscales. The benefits of this approach include more options being available to the designer, a reduced need for extensive and costly testing and more efficient and shorter design iteration cycles. This will lead to more versatile, more cost-effective, and more efficient composite products, and thus help to fulfill the promise of composite materials.

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REFERENCES

1. Whitehead, R. S. and Deo, R. B. "A Building Block Approach to Design Verification Testing of Primary Composite Structures" *Proceedings of the 24th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS SDM Conference*, Lake Tahoe, Nevada, 473-477, 1983.
2. Tsai, S. W. "A Survey of Macroscopic Failure Criteria for Composite Materials", *J. Reinf. Plas. Comp.*, **3**, 40-62, 1984.
3. Chamis, C. C., "Mechanics of Composite Materials - Past, Present and Future", *J. Comp. Tech. Res.*, **11**, 3-14, 1989.
4. Whitney, J. M. and Nuismer, R. J., "Stress Fracture Criteria for Laminated Composites Containing Stress Concentrations", *J. Comp. Mater.*, **8**, 253-265, 1974.
5. Mar, J. W. and Lin, K. Y., "Fracture of Boron/Aluminum Composites with Discontinuities", *J. Comp. Mater.*, **11**, 405-421, 1977.

6. Ashby, M. F., "Physical Modeling of Materials Problems", *Mat. Sci. Tech.*, **8**, 102-111, 1992.
7. Bunsell, A. R. (Editor). *Fiber Reinforcements for Composite Materials*, Elsevier, 1988.
8. Weibull, W., "A Statistical Distribution Function of Wide Applicability", *J. Appl. Mech.*, **293**, 1951.
9. Curtin, W. A., "Theory of Mechanical Properties of Ceramic-Matrix Composites", *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, **74**, 2837-45, 1991.
10. Harlow, D. G. and Phoenix, S. L., "The Chain-of-Bundles Probability Model for the Strength of Fibrous Materials I: Analysis and Conjectures", *J. Comp. Mat.*, **12**, 195-214, 1978.
11. Aveston, J., Cooper, G. A., and Kelly, A., "Single and Multiple Fracture in the Properties of Fiber Composites", Conf. Proc., National Physical Laboratory, IPC Science and Technology Press, 15-26, 1971.
12. Evans, A. G. and Zok, F. W., "The Physics and Mechanics of Fibre-reinforced Brittle Matrix Composites", *J. Mat. Sci.*, **28**, 3857-3896, 1994.
13. Hitchon, J. W., and Phillips, D. C. "The Effect of Specimen Size on the Strength of CFRP", *Composites*, **9**, 119-124, 1978.
14. Ogin, S. L., Smith, P. A., Beaumont, P. W. R., "Matrix Cracking and Stiffness Reduction during the fatigue of a (90/0)s GFRP Laminate", *J. Comp. Sci. Tech.*, **24**, 23-31, 1985.
15. Dvorak, G. J. and Laws, N., "Analysis of First Ply Failure in Composite Laminates", *Eng. Fract. Mech.*, **25**, 763-770, 1986.
16. Xia, Z. C., Carr, R. R., and Hutchinson, J. W., "Transverse Cracking in Fiber-Reinforced Brittle Matrix, Cross-Ply Laminates", *Acta Metall. et Mater.*, **41**, 2365-2376, 1993.
17. Maddocks, J. R., *Microcracking in Composite Laminates Under Thermal and Mechanical Loading*, TELAC Report 95-2, MIT, 1995.
18. Lagace, P. A. and Brewer, J. C., "Quadratic Stress Criterion for Initiation of Delamination", *J. Comp. Mat.*, **22**, 1141-1155, 1988.
19. O'Brien, T. K., "Characterization of Delamination Onset and Growth in a Composite Laminate", *ASTM STP 775*, 140-167, 1982.
20. Hutchinson, J. W. and Suo, Z., "Mixed Mode Cracking in Layered Materials", *Applied Mech. Review.*, **28**, 63-191, 1991.
21. Salpekar, S. A. and O'Brien, T. K., "Combined Effect of Matrix Cracking and Stress-Free Edge on Delamination", *ASTM STP 1110*, 287-311, 1993.
22. Bhat, N. V., *Delamination growth in Graphite/Epoxy Composite Laminates Under Tensile Loading*, TELAC Report 93-10, MIT, 1993.
23. Jamison, R. D., "On the Interrelationship between Fiber Fracture and Ply Cracking in Graphite/Epoxy Laminates", *ASTM STP 907*, 252-273, 1986.
24. Sun, C. T., and Jen, K. C., "On the Effect of Matrix Cracks on Laminate Strength", *J. Reinf. Plas. Comp.*, **6**, 208-222, 1987.
25. Harris, C. E and Morris, D. H. *Fracture Behaviour of Thick, Laminated Graphite Epoxy Composites*, NASA Contractor Report 3784, 1984.
26. Awerbuch, J. and Madhukar, M. S., "Notched Strength of Composite Laminates: Predictions and Experiments-A Review", *J. Reinf. Plas. Comp.*, **4**, 3-159, 1985.
27. Mandell, J. F., Wang, S. S., and McGarry, F. J. "The Extension of Crack Tip Damage Zones in Fiber Reinforced Plastic Laminates", *J. Comp. Mat.*, **9**, 266-287, 1975.
28. Peters, P. W. M., "On the Increasing Fracture Toughness at Increasing Notch Length of 0/90 and 0/±45/0 Graphite/Epoxy Laminates", *Composites*, **14**, 365-369 1983.
29. Lagace, P. A., Bhat, N. V., Gundogdu, A., "Response of Notched Graphite/Epoxy and Graphite/PEEK Systems", *ASTM STP 1110*, 55-71, 1993.
30. Kortschot M. T. and Beaumont, P. W. R., "Damage-Based Notched Strength Modeling: A Summary", *ASTM STP 1110*, 617-637, 1991.
31. Spearing, S. M., Kortschot, M. T., and Beaumont, P. W. R., "The Fatigue Damage Mechanics of Notched Carbon Fibre/PEEK Laminates", *Composites*, **23**, 305-311, 1992.
32. Chang, F-K. and Lessard, L. B., "Damage Tolerance of Laminated Composites Containing an Open Hole and Subjected to Compressive Loadings: Part I - Analysis", *J. Comp. Mater.*, **25**, 2-43, 1991.
33. Graves, M. J. and Lagace, P. A., "Damage Tolerance of Composite Cylinders", *Composite Structures*, **4**, 75-91 1985.
34. Saeger, K. J. and Lagace, P. A., "Fracture of Pressurized Composite Cylinders with a High Strain to Failure Matrix System", *ASTM STP 907*, 326-337, 1986.
35. Budiman, H. T. and Lagace, P. A., "Nondimensional Parameters for Geometric Nonlinear Effects in Pressurized Cylinders with Axial Cracks", Submitted to *J. Appl. Mech.*